

APPLICATION OF EMBEDDED SMALL-DIAMETER FIBER BRAGG GRATING SENSORS FOR FABRICATION AND HEALTH MONITORING OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT: Small-diameter fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors, whose outside diameter was 52 μm , were applied for the detection of delaminations in carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates. Reflection spectra from the embedded FBG sensors deformed because of the change in the strain distribution due to a delamination. Since these deformations of the spectra could be reproduced by theoretical calculations, it was found that the small-diameter FBG sensors could detect the occurrence of the delamination caused by a cyclic loading or a low-velocity impact and evaluate the delamination length quantitatively. Furthermore, the reflection spectrum was measured during the fabrication process of the laminates in order to investigate the birefringence effect due to thermal residual stress.

KEYWORDS: small-diameter FBG sensor, CFRP laminates, delamination, health monitoring, thermal residual stress.

INTRODUCTION

FBG sensors are very sensitive to non-uniform strain distribution along the entire length of the gratings [1]. The strain distribution deforms the reflection spectrum from the FBG sensors. Taking advantage of the sensitivity, the authors applied FBG sensors for detecting transverse cracks that caused non-uniform strain distribution in CFRP laminates [2]. However, the cladding of common optical fibers is 125 μm in diameter, which is almost the same as the normal thickness of one ply in CFRP laminates. Thus, when the normal FBG sensors are embedded into CFRP composites, there is a possibility that the optical fibers might deteriorate the mechanical properties of the laminates. In order to prevent the deterioration, small-diameter FBG sensors have recently been developed by the authors and Hitachi Cable Ltd. [3]. The outside diameter of the polyimide coating is 52 μm , and the cladding is 40 μm in diameter.

The small-diameter FBG sensors could also detect transverse cracks in CFRP laminates sensitively [4]. In this research, this technique was applied for detection of edge delaminations in the laminates under cyclic loading and delaminations caused by low-velocity impact. Furthermore, the reflection spectrum was measured during the fabrication process of the laminates in order to investigate the birefringence effect due to thermal residual stress, which disturbed the form of the spectrum.

DETECTION OF EDGE DELAMINATION UNDER CYCLIC LOADING

Experimental Procedure

Bragg gratings were fabricated in small-diameter optical fibers. The outside diameters of the polyimide coating, the cladding, and the core are 52 μm , 40 μm , and 6.5 μm , respectively. The grating length is 10mm, and the grating period is about 0.5 μm . The FBG sensor was embedded in a 90° ply in contact with a 0°/90° interface of a CFRP T700S/2500 quasi-isotropic laminate (Toray Industries, Inc.) whose laminate configuration was [+45/-45/0/90]_s. The FBG sensor of 10mm gauge length was located at the position of 0 to 10mm from the center of the specimen as shown in Fig. 1.

Cyclic tensile load was applied to the specimen from 0 to 440MPa at room temperature. The frequency of the loading cycle was 5Hz. After the cyclic loading was stopped at the pre-determined numbers of cycles, the reflection spectra from the FBG sensor were measured at both stress levels of 0MPa and 220MPa using an ASE light source unit (Ando Electric Co., Ltd., AQ6310(155)) and an

optical spectrum analyzer (Ando Electric Co., Ltd., AQ6317).

Fig. 1 Embedding of a small-diameter FBG sensor into a CFRP quasi-isotropic laminate.

Fig. 2 Soft X-ray photograph of the specimen and definition of the edge delamination length L_{ed} .

Experimental Results

Figure 2 shows a soft X-ray photograph of the specimen in which the edge delaminations occurred after loading cycles of 100,000. In this study, an edge delamination length L_{ed} was defined as the length of a delamination in the width direction and determined from the X-ray photograph. The edge delamination grew with an increase in number of cycles as summarized in Table 1. The spectra measured at each step are shown in Fig. 3. The intensity of the spectrum was normalized by the highest component. Before the cyclic load was applied to the specimen (step 0), the spectrum had one peak. After the occurrence of the delamination, though the drastic change in the form of the spectrum measured after unloading was not observed in all steps, the spectrum measured at the stress level of 220MPa changed its form with an increase in the delamination length. When the tip of the edge delamination reached the position of the FBG sensor (step3), the spectrum was divided into two peaks. As the delamination length increased (from step 3 to step 4), the intensity of the longer wavelength peak increased relatively.

Table 1 Edge delamination length at various number of cycles.

	Number of cycles ($\times 10^3$)	Edge delamination length (mm)
Step 0	0	0
Step 1	1	2.8
Step 2	20	5.2
Step 3	100	7.4
Step 4	1000	9.0

Analysis

For confirmation of the measured results, the reflection spectrum was simulated by theoretical analysis. First, the axial strain distribution in the small-diameter fiber embedded in a laminate was calculated by 3-D FEM analysis with ABAQUS code. The FEM model was just 1/8 part of the test specimen and consisted of a glass optical fiber, a polyimide coating and a CFRP laminate. The edge delamination at $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface or in the middle of the 90° ply was assumed as quadrilateral shape, and the thermal residual stress was introduced by cooling from the manufacturing temperature of 130°C to the room temperature of 25°C . Next, the distributions of the grating period and the average refractive index of the FBG were calculated from the axial strain distribution [5]. Then the reflection spectrum was simulated from the distributions by solving couple mode equations with transfer matrix method [6].

Fig. 3 Measured reflection spectrum

Figure 4 shows the calculated spectra after unloading. When the edge delamination is assumed to exist in the middle of the 90° ply, the spectrum does not change. This is because the delamination in that position hardly disturbs the distribution of the longitudinal thermal residual strain. On the other hand, when the edge delamination appears at the 0°/90° interface and the L_{ed} is over 5 mm, the spectrum has two peaks. In this case, the compression by the delamination, so that the axial strain distribution consists of two strain level at the delaminated area corresponds to the longer wavelength and the smaller strain level at the bonded area corresponds to the shorter wavelength. Thus, the intensity of the longer wavelength peak increases with an increase

Figure 5 shows the calculated spectra under loading of 220 MPa longitudinally, the bonded area is compressed by Poisson's effect, and the intensity ratio of the two peaks in the spectrum increases. Hence, the intensity of the longer wavelength peak in the spectrum increases, and the spectrum for the case of 0°/90° interface delamination also has two peaks. These results indicate that the edge delamination will be easily detected by applying a tensile loading.

Fig. 6 Intensity ratios of the two peaks against L_{ed} .

Fig. 4 Calculated spectra after unloading.

Fig. 5 Calculated spectra under loading of 220MPa.

Compared with these calculated spectra in Figs. 4 and 5, the measured spectra in Fig. 3 show the same tendency of the deformation as the case of the 90° intralaminar delamination. When a cross section of the specimen after the cyclic loading was observed, the edge delamination existed in the 90° ply. Thus, these calculation results are consistent with the experimental results. From these results, the intensities of the two peaks in the spectrum were found to correspond to the lengths of delaminated and bonded areas. Thus, the intensity ratio of the two peaks I_L/I_S is defined as an indicator to evaluate the delamination size. Here, I_L and I_S are the intensities of the longer and shorter wavelength peaks,

respectively. Figure 6 shows the logarithmic plot of the intensity ratio against L_{ed} . Both the experimental and calculated results have the same tendency that the I_L/I_S increases with an increase in L_{ed} . Thus the delamination length L_{ed} can be estimated from the intensity ratio I_L/I_S . Moreover, as shown in Fig. 5, the distance between the two peaks in the spectrum can indicate whether the edge delamination grew at the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface or in the middle of the 90° ply.

DETECTION OF DELAMINATION INDUCED BY LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT

Low-velocity impact easily induces delaminations and matrix cracks in CFRP laminates, which are barely visible from the outer surface. For practical use of the CFRP laminates, it is important to monitor the damage state in real time. In this chapter, the above detection technique is applied to the delamination induced by low-velocity impact.

Experimental Procedure

The specimen was CFRP laminates T700S/2500, and the laminate configuration was cross-ply $[0_4/90_4/0_4]$. The dimensions of the test specimen were $100 \times 100 \times 1.5 \text{ mm}^3$. The impact loading was applied to the specimen with a drop-weight impact tester (Instron Corporation, Dynatup Mini-Tower). The applied impact energies were 1.0J, 2.0J, and 3.0J. After the impact test, interfacial delaminations were observed by an ultrasonic C-scan. The schematic of the damages in the laminate are illustrated in Fig. 7. Furthermore, cross-sectional micrographs at P, Q, and R planes in Fig. 7 are shown in Fig. 8. Typical damages in the laminate were two peanut-shape delaminations at upper and lower $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interfaces, shear cracks in 90° ply, and a bending crack in lower 0° ply. The small-diameter FBG sensor was embedded into 90° ply in contact with the lower $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface as shown in Fig.7 in order to detect the delamination at the lower interface. The reflection spectrum from the embedded FBG was measured using the optical spectrum analyzer after the impact test.

Fig. 7 Schematic of the specimen configurations and typical damages in the cross-ply laminate.

Fig. 8 Cross-sectional micrographs of the damaged laminates.

Experimental Results

Figure 9 shows photographs of the lower $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interfacial delamination observed by ultrasonic C-scan. The size of the delamination increased with an increase in the impact energy level. A bending crack also appeared in all the pictures. The reflection spectra measured before and after the impact tests were shown in Fig. 10. These were normalized by the intensity of the highest component. When the impact energy was 1.0J, the delamination did not reach to the FBG sensor and the bending crack passed under the sensor. In this case, the reflection spectrum was deformed drastically. At the impact energy of 2.0J, the tip of the delamination passed through the FBG sensor, and the reflection spectrum

had one large peak at the higher wavelength and some small components at the lower wavelength. Then, when the impact energy was increased to 3.0J, the delamination covered the entire gauge length of the FBG sensor, and the reflection spectrum shifted its center wavelength without the deformation.

Fig. 9 Photographs of the lower $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$ interfacial delamination observed by ultrasonic C-scan.

Fig. 10 Measured reflection spectra.

Analysis

Also, these experimental results were confirmed by theoretical calculations in the same way as the analysis procedure described in the above chapter. The 1/4 part of the specimen was modeled by using 3D finite elements. In this model, the lower $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$ interface delamination, shear cracks in 90° ply and a bending crack in the lower 0° ply were introduced. From the analysis, the strain distribution at $27\mu\text{m}$ above from the lower $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$ interface, where the center of the optical fiber was located, was obtained. Then, the reflection spectrum was simulated using the axial strain distribution. The calculated spectra are shown in Fig. 11. These shapes of the spectra well reproduced those of the measured ones in Fig. 10. This agreement indicates that the deformation of the spectrum at the impact energy of 1.0J is caused by the strain concentration around the tip of the bending crack. The large peak at the longer wavelength in the spectrum at 2.0J corresponds to the strain at the delaminated area, and the some components at the shorter wavelength are caused by the change in the strain distribution around the delamination tip. The spectrum at 3.0J is not deformed, because the whole gauge length of the FBG is covered with the delamination and is under uniform strain. The center wavelength shift of the spectrum by the impact of 3.0J corresponds to the strain difference between the bonded and the

(a) Impact energy = 1.0J (b) Impact energy = 2.0J (c) Impact energy = 3.0J

Fig. 11 Calculated reflection spectra, which correspond to the measured spectra in Fig. 10. delaminated areas. From these results, it was found that the small-diameter FBG sensor could detect the delamination induced by low-velocity impacts.

EFFECT OF THERMAL RESIDUAL STRESS ON THE FORM OF THE REFLECTION SPECTRUM

As shown in Figs. 3 and 10, the reflection spectra already had slight deformation just after the fabrication of the laminates. This deformation of the spectrum will lead to misreading in damage detection. Thus, the reflection spectrum was observed during the fabrication process of a laminate. The small-diameter FBG sensor was embedded in the 0° ply in contact with the 90° ply of a cross-ply laminate $[0_2/90_4/0_2]$. During the manufacture of the laminate using a hot-press procedure, the reflection spectra from the embedded FBG sensor were obtained at various temperatures. Fig. 12 shows the reflection spectra measured during the cooling process of the cure cycle. The spectrum at 185°C has the same form as that measured before embedment, and the spectrum was disturbed as the laminate was cooled to room temperature.

Fig. 12 Reflection spectra measured during the cooling process of the cure cycle.

In order to confirm that the change in the form of the spectrum was due to thermal residual stress, the spectrum was calculated theoretically. All strain components due to thermal residual stress at the core of the embedded FBG sensor were calculated using FEM analysis on the assumption that the laminate was under the generalized plane strain condition. From the strain components obtained at the core, the grating period Λ and the average refractive indices n_p and n_q along principal axes were calculated [5]. When the birefringence effect is induced, light wave propagates polarizing along the two principal planes that have different refractive indices n_p and n_q . Since the two polarization modes have different wavelengths according to the n_p and n_q , reflected waves from the FBG have different Bragg wavelengths. Thus, two power spectra R_p and R_q corresponding to the n_p and n_q were calculated separately. Then, the reflection spectrum disturbed by the birefringence effect was obtained by superposition of R_p and R_q [7, 8]. Fig. 13 shows the calculated reflection spectra. Compared with the measured spectra in Fig. 12, the calculated results well reproduce the change in the form of the spectrum. This agreement indicates that the change in the spectrum was caused by the thermal residual stress.

Fig. 13 Calculated reflection spectra affected by thermal residual stress, which correspond to the measured spectra in Fig. 12.

CONCLUSIONS

In this research, newly developed small-diameter FBG sensors, whose outside diameter was 52 μ m, were applied to detect delaminations in CFRP laminates. First, for the detection of the edge delamination, the FBG sensor was embedded into the 90° ply of a quasi-isotropic laminate [+45/-45/0/90]_s. As the edge delamination length increased under cyclic loading, two peaks appeared in the reflection spectrum, and those intensities changed depending on the delamination length. This deformation of the spectrum could be reproduced by theoretical calculations. Hence, it was found that the delamination length could be predicted using the intensity ratio of the two peaks, and the distance between the two peaks indicated whether the delamination grew at the 0°/90° interface or in the middle of the 90° ply.

Secondly, this technique was applied to the detection of the delamination induced by low-velocity impacts. The small-diameter FBG sensor was embedded into the 90° ply of a cross-ply laminate [0₄/90₄/0₄], and a low-velocity impact was applied to the laminate at three levels of impact energies: 1.0J, 2.0J, and 3.0J. As a result, the reflection spectrum was deformed depending on the delamination size, and this change agreed with theoretical calculations. Thus, the small-diameter FBG sensor could also detect the delamination induced by low-velocity impacts.

Furthermore, the reflection spectrum was measured during the fabrication process of the laminates. The deformation of the spectrum during the cooling process could be reproduced by the theoretical calculation considering the birefringence effect due to thermal residual stress. Thus, the deformation was found to be caused by the thermal residual stress. If this phenomenon is used, the thermal residual stress will be evaluated from the deformation of the reflection spectrum.

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